

Assignment of Carbon Budgets at Regional Level: the PLEDGES Model.

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The concept of a carbon budget has been well defined and assessed at a global level (Committee On Climate Change, 2009) (Levin, 2013) (Rogelj et al., 2019), but just a few countries around the world have started to consider this concept (Green Economy Coalition, 2023) to shape cumulative emissions limits at the regional level. Not setting carbon budgets at regional levels implies the 2°C of global warming target committed by the Paris Agreement may not be met as a temperature limit concerns the cumulative emissions stocked in the atmosphere. To fill this gap, the PLEDGES (Pledge Limits Evaluation for Decarbonization: Goals of EU27 Strategy) project introduces a novel simulation tool that seeks to encompass, for the first time, the complete range of carbon budget distribution among the European Union (EU27) Member States (MSs) while attaining the Green Deal (European Commission, 2021) objectives (reducing emissions by -55% compared to 2005 and achieving EU carbon neutrality by 2050) and the 2°C target. The PLEDGES tool is focused on EU geographical level, but it might be easily adapted to other geographical regions in future works.

Once a carbon budget for EU27 is assessed (Perissi et al., 2018), (Trio, 2022), (Duscha et al., 2019), the PLEDGES tool can manage likely emissions deviations from the budget due to unexpected increases in emissions in one MS and dynamically reallocate this to other MSs in an optimal way. This is, for instance, the recent case of Germany: because of the geopolitical situation in Ukraine, the country re-activated coal power plants to reduce its dependency on gas and secure the national gas supply. In facing this increase, the PLEDGES approach involves assessing the potential of each MS in trying to compensate for the increase, with the final purpose of keeping the EU27 budget within the established limit. In distributing the responsibility for emissions reduction and in planning a strategy for compensating emissions, the model adopts an "effort-sharing" approach based on a combination of factors such as inertia, economic capability to pay for mitigations, and the degree of economic decoupling (Perissi and Jones, 2023a) of each MS. An early version of the model's aims and structure has been already discussed at the SW23 workshop (2023) and published in the Conference proceedings (Perissi and Jones, 2023b), which we refer to for a detailed description without duplicating that content here.

In the present work, we progressed toward the tool implementation, considering the emissions balancing per Economic Sector and the Emissions Trading Dynamic among MSs. The budget assigned to each Member State is allocated to the economic sectors (Figure 1) according to the inertia principle (default option) or with specific criteria set by the user. Differently from the earlier version, the possible increase (or decrease) of emissions is now simulated at the economic sector level (energy sector in Germany, according to the previous example). The economic sectors classification in the model comes from the European Energy Agency (EEA) (Eurostat, 2021). Once the deviation from the national budget occurs,

and the compensation strategy achieved based on the effort sharing approach, each Member States will have a new carbon quota to meet.

Figure 1. The PLEDGES model structure, including economic sectors.

The MS can either reduce all the required amount of emissions by itself or it can choose to buy or sell in the market. This second choice allows the “Gains from Trade” (Samuelson, 1939) dynamic, represented qualitatively by the causal loop diagrams in Figure 2. Setting an initial exogenous price (P) for emissions quotas at EU level then a supply and demand dynamics of quotas determines the evolution of the quotas’ P. The supply and demand of quotas arise from the possibility for Member States to sell or purchase quotas, according to the cost of available abatement technologies/solutions. The abatement costs are implemented in the model by means the MS Abatement Cost curve designed in a look up table (France MAC etc.). If the initial P for the emissions quota permit is set at the EU27 market level and the quota to be recovered from MS1 results in a price lower than P, it implies that MS1 can abate this quota at a lower cost than the market, enabling it to sell permits to cover emissions elsewhere. Vice versa, if MS1 can abate emissions at a higher cost than the initial EU27 price, it will purchase quotas from other MSs whose abatement cost allows for a cheaper solution. The quotas to be bought or sold for each MS are summed up: all the quotas that can be sold across the MSs constitute the "supply," while all the quotas to be bought represent the "demand."

Figure 2. PLEDGES model Gains from Trade dynamic, based on 3 Member States network.

The initial price evolves until supply quotas offsets demand quotas, establishing the new price at which the adopted compensation can be achieved across the MSs. As a limit, the MAC implemented is static. The true abatement curve will not follow a marginal cost change but rather deep change that follows with investment and deployment of technology resulting in feedbacks that decrease costs and lead to new opportunities for emissions reduction. This is another research field which will be further investigated by the authors to complete the model purpose.

The PLEDGES tool is focused on EU geographical level, but due to its relatively simple structures, can be easily adapted to simulate national carbon trading in other regions.

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